

THE MOST BENEFICIAL TECHNIQUES FOR READING, LISTENING AND WRITING SKILLS

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Annotation. This article illustrates different methods and techniques for English skills, such as, reading, listening, writing skills. General conclusions are given about easy ways to use them, their place of use and how important they are for students. As well as, it talks about why you can get good results in exams by using them.

Annotatsiya. Bu maqola o'qish, tinglash, yozish uchun turli tuman metodlar va texnikalarni ko'rsatadi. Ulardan foydalanishning oson usullari, foydalanish o'rni hamda o'quvchilar uchun qanchalik ahamiyatliligi haqida umumiy xulosalar beriladi. Nima uchun ulardan foydalanish orqali imtihonlarda yaxshi natijalarga erishish mumkinligi haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Абстрактный. В этой статье представлены различные методы и приемы чтения, аудирования и письма. В ней приводятся общие выводы о том насколько их легко использовать где они используются и насколько они важны для учащихся. В нем рассказывается о том почему с их помощью можно получить хорошие результаты на экзаменах.

Key words. Preview the text, annotate, clues, flashcards, subvocalization, listening, reading, writing, take notes, clarifying questions, take breaks, practice, brainstorm ideas, outline, rough draft, proofread, grammar, feedback, audio sources, effort.

I. INTRODUCTION.

In today's developing world, learning new languages is important in every field. Therefore, we have to utilize some kind of techniques in order to making easier our tasks and achieving our target scores. Especially, we should know great ways to use IELTS and Multilevel systems exams for skills – listening, reading, writing. So there are some techniques for them. And this tips will help you improve your skills, even when you have short time and busy life. Because we all have work, study, family, household chores and it is hard to fit any English practice into the day.

II. Methods and ways.

Reading. It is one of extremely challenging and significant task in the exams. However, there are some tips, for example:

1) **READING** articles—depending on your level of English, you could read the latest news on a newspapers, platforms, websites, or you could read articles which are written specially for learners of acquiring the language.

2) Moreover, one of the best way to improve your reading is learning and memorizing vocabularies. And students should try to guess their meaning from the context, also take notes, look through the dictionaries. Download or pocket dictionaries enhance vocabularies. And you should keep vocabulary journal. When you practice reading tasks, firstly, skim headings, subheadings, and visuals to get a general idea of the content. Secondly, formulate questions

about the topic before and during reading. And next, You should briefly summarize each section or chapter in your own words.

3) Make a plan , in other words, set yourself a goal of reading at least 2 or more times a week

4) Novels are significant way to enhance reading skills . Firstly, what genre interest you, this is because, it is beneficial to get rid of boredom.

Listening tips. Listening is one of the easiest task and it is the best way to get high score from exams. Like other skills , a lot of exercises and practice is important part of it. First, you should find your interest subject to listen podcasts, videos, movies . This is productive for improve passive and general listening skills .Secondly, Exercising listening assignments is also fruitful , especially , after doing it, you need to analyze them, as well working with new vocabularies.

Thirdly, always keep the learning consistent and habitual. Utilizing symbols and abbreviations for frequently used words, phrases or names are useful for notes and saving time.

Be careful to these:

1. Shadowing and learn under the pronunciation will help the listening
2. Don't fear and funk if you don't understand something from it, because it can be cause to mistake with others
3. Use subtitles in English. Watch and listen 5 minute with subtitle, and without it.
4. Take note -- mark key points and main ideas. Paraphrase what you hear that helpful to understand and remember what you hear.
5. When you do exercise listening , you should try to save time, which

Writing tips.

First and foremost, understanding the task question is the first and essential part of writing. And then , planning and outlining, by the other words, you should brainstorm the ideas. Next, organize your ideas into a logical structure. Like other skills, writing also require much practice. Knowing complex and compound structures, using advanced vocabularies and linking words play crucial part of writing essays, letters.

Revise and review your work for clarity, correct, coherence and grammar errors. Proofread -- you may check for typos and spelling mistakes.

Working with a people to check and give feedback. Exploring different types of texts, like novels, articles, and essay examples .

Remember, improving your reading, listening, and writing skills takes time and effort. Be patient, persistent and most importantly, have fun.

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